

ADAPTING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE JIU VALLEY COMPANIES FOR THE TRANSITION TO A SUSTAINABLE, CLIMATE-NEUTRAL ECONOMY

Ramona ROSULESCU ¹, Eduard EDELHAUSER ²
Position: PhD Student¹, Prof., PhD²
University of Petroșani
Petroșani, Universității Str., No. 20, Romania
ramona_rosulescu@yahoo.com¹, eduardedelhauser@upet.ro ²,
<https://www.upet.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose –The study aim is to find employment solutions for young and able-bodied workers from unemployment of many families in Jiu Valley, left without a job and failing to benefit from local opportunities, and also for parents that must left their children in care the community or other families and choose the path of migration outside the Jiu Valley or even the country.

Methodology/approach - The Jiu Valley is distinguished as one of the most suffering regions in Romania based on the problems stemming from the negative impact of layoffs following the closure mines since 1995, which generated high unemployment, the dislocation of young people and adults, poverty and exclusion. The research methodology was based on an analyses of the past 30 years management of the mining industry, and finding a recovery plan for this region.

Findings –The global economic context but also the inadequate management of the mining exploitation for the last 30 years in the Jiu Valley, led to a tragic situation, and the only solution for the recovery of the Jiu Valley may be the use of non-refundable funds in developing viable economic alternatives for the maintaining of the economic activity.

Research limitations/implications –Even if the proposed solution are developed in the technologies from the field of energy from renewable sources, the solutions may be generalized in production of rechargeable batteries or the production of hydrogen and hydrogen-based synthetic fuels.

Practical implications - The population of the area is heavily affected by the decline of the mining industry and exposed to severe risks on the social dimension due to low economic development which does not allow the attraction of investors and determines the lack of a positive evolution at all the important levels that contribute to the quality of life, especially education, medical services and social assistance. The study represent a basis for fixing these structural problems of this former mining region.

Originality/value – The purpose of this research is to find the best method for adapting the management of the Jiu Valley companies for the transition to a sustainable, climate-neutral economy, but also to propose a solution to stop the population decline and to continue the economic activity in the Jiu Valley.

Key words: Adaptive management, Transition, Renewable sources

Introduction and background literature

Current global mining issues

The last 30 years have meant the decline of world mining and the closure of numerous mining fields, that have led to huge economic and social problems, fact reflected in numerous studies. (Dale B., 2002), (Haney M., 2013), (Horvath G., 2012), (Cardoso A., 2015) and (Radu B., 2016)

A recent study of Deloitte shows that 50% of the mining engineers will be retired in 10 years. In USA the 220.000 workers from the mining sector will be retired until 2030, and in Canada 100.000.

Figure 1. The labor shortage in the mining industry of developed countries

Source: Deloitte - https://www.deloitte.com/content/dam/assets-shared/legacy/docs/gx-Tracking-the-trends-2023_Digital_V2.pdf

Another report, presented by McKinsey demonstrate that teenagers are certainly no more interested to work in the mining sector or in the oil gas sector.

Mining is not attractive to young talent.

Share of respondents, ages 15 to 30, who would consider working in the following sectors, %

Figure 2. Has mining lost its luster? Why talent is moving elsewhere and how to bring them back

Source: McKinsey - <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/metals-and-mining/our-insights/has-mining-lost-its-luster-why-talent-is-moving-elsewhere-and-how-to-bring-them-back>

The decline of Hunedoara County and the mining industry extinction in the Jiu Valley

The economic-social impact until 2030 of the transition of the Hunedoara county was analyzed in a study carried out by the Frankfurt School of Finance and Management financed by the Support Program for Structural Reforms of the EU. The study used a macro econometric model for the analysis of the effects of the transition at the territory level, but the modeling was carried out before the timing and extent of the measures, through which the PNRR considerably accelerated the implementation of the PNIESC.

Even so, in terms of expected changes in employment, the model shows a considerable imbalance between loss (7.400 jobs) and generation (1.700 jobs) in occupations requiring a level of training basic or medium. In terms of gross added value (GVA), however, the impact of the transition leads to an increase in this indicator in most of the analyzed sectors. Along with the job losses, the county was also selected as a result of the socio-economic context marked by persistent disparities that will deepen if the acceleration of the transition to climate neutrality is not accompanied by mitigation measures:

Population decline - The resident population in 2019 was 379,987 inhabitants. The territory showed a sharp downward trend of 8.9% in the period 2012 - 2020 of the global population, while the downward trend of the working-age population was in the same period of 13.8%.

Three quarters of the population in deprived areas - In the disadvantaged areas of the county, identified at the UAT level, initially in accordance with GEO 24/98 and, later, according to GEO 75/2000, live approx. 250,000 people. Disadvantaged areas include, along with rural localities, the cities of Jiu Valley: Lupeni, Petroșani, Vulcan, Petritla, Aninoasa and Uricani.

Incomes consistently below the national average and energy poverty - Regarding the average net salary, it was in the period 2010 – 2020 below the national average by approx. 18%. In the last 4 years, it was 19% below the national average. The territory records an energy poverty rate of 70% in winter and 45% compared to the whole year.

High level of unemployment - In December 2021, 6,231 unemployed people were registered in the territory, of which 2,978 were women. The unemployment rate was 3.64% in December 2021 compared to the national average of 2.69%. Hunedoara is the territory affected by the transition that had the most dramatic decrease in the active population (13.8%) in the period 2012-2020.

The high share of exposed labor in industry and the modest technological level of the production of goods and services - The labor force employed in the industry represents 28.7%, with a pronounced trend of 30% decrease between 2008 and 2019. Regarding the technological level of the production of goods at the county level, in 2019, high technology was used in 1.2% of the total production, and medium high technology was used in 24.08% of the production.

Insufficient development of renewable energy production capacities - According to the latest data published by Transelectrica in May 2020, in Hunedoara county, the production capacity of photovoltaic energy in operation (power with PIF, according to issuers) totaled only 1.51 MW, respectively 0.11% of the entire installed capacity of photovoltaic energy .

Considering the above, Hunedoara county was selected for mitigating the effects of the transition to climate neutrality.

EU Commission and Romanian Government solutions

The Just Transition Fund represent an essential tool for supporting the territories most affected by the transition to climate neutrality and avoiding the deepening of regional disparities.

Figure 3. Just Transition Fund Territories

Source https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/just-transition-fund/just-transition-platform_en

Figure 4. The twelve functional areas from seven EU countries
 Source <https://functionalareas.eu/>

The Just Transition Program (JTP) aims to mitigate the impact of the closure or transformation of dominant economic activities in the local economy of 6 counties in Romania – Gorj, Hunedoara, Dolj, Galați, Prahova and Mureș and to facilitate their transition to climate neutrality.

Methodology

Our study is based on the solutions offered by the project “Strategy for the transition from coal of the Jiu Valley”, where PwC developed ten concept project and selected in consultation with key stakeholders. There is also an additional ten project concepts that has been developed by START.

Figure 5. Jiu Valley Development Strategy – overview of themes and intervention areas (source - From Strategy to Action: Delivering a Just Transition in the Jiu Valley, today and tomorrow- Initiative for coal regions in transition Supporting a just transition)

Given the limited potential for the creation of jobs only through investments at the level of SMEs, at the level of the territory were identified a series of economic activities

- Manufacture of rechargeable batteries, battery packs and accumulators for transports
- Manufacture of hydrogen and hydrogen-based synthetic fuels, an equipment for the production and use of hydrogen
- Manufacture of equipment for the energy efficiency of buildings such as pumps of heat, windows, doors, exterior wall systems, roof systems, products insulators, household appliances, hot water systems housekeeping and cooling / ventilation systems
- The manufacture of technologies in the field of energy from renewable sources
- Manufacture of biogas and biofuels intended for use in transport, such as and bioliquids;
- Production of electricity from non-fossil gaseous and liquid fuels from sources
- Sorting and processing non-hazardous waste streams collected separately for the purpose transformation into secondary raw materials

Figure 6. Overview of proposed transition projects

(Source - From Strategy to Action: Delivering a Just Transition in the Jiu Valley, today and tomorrow- Initiative for coal regions in transition Supporting a just transition)

Findings and discussions

The last 27 years, led Jiu Valley, a former pillar of the Romanian mining industry to disaster.

Management in Jiu Valley mining industry during the period 1997-2024. RAH – CNH – SNH – SNIMVJ – CEH – CEVJ a managerial disaster of the mining industry

After 1990, the inefficiency of mining activities was masked by subsidies, but even so the numerical decline of the mining industry could not be halted.

Figure 7. 24 years of evolution of the Romanian extractive industry measured in number of employees

(source – Romanian National Institute of Statistics)

In figure 6 it is obvious that in 25 years, the number of employees in the mining industry was reduced 5 times.

The Romanian management of bituminous coal mining in the last 35 years has been a disaster. Thus, even if this economic activity carried out in Jiu Valley took place under several names, they were only branches of the same poorly managed activity. Bituminous coal exploitation carried the logo of Autonomous Bituminous Company (RAH), immediately after 1990, then, starting with 1998, it was called the National Bituminous Company (CNH), transformed into the National Bituminous Firm (SNH) in the 2010s, and immediately divided in 2011 into The National Society of Mine Closures Jiu Valley (SNIMVJ) and into Hunedoara Energetic Complex (CEH), and finally in 2022 SNIMVJ transformed into Jiu Valley Energy Complex (CEVJ). The longest-lived mining companies in the bituminous coal mining field, CNH and CEH, disappeared along the way, having a history of 26 years out of the 35 years of post-communist mining in the Jiu Valley, but they disappeared leaving behind a hole of 7 billion lei at the state budget of Romania, i.e. 35% of the total debts that the Romanian state companies have to the state budget.

In 1998 by Government Decision no. 806/1998, Autonomous Bituminous Company (RAH) was transformed into the National Bituminous Company (CNH). The disappearance of CNH was revealed in 2011 by the first author of this paper, in several dozens of journalistic investigations that revealed empty promises, damage to the state budget and lack of managerial vision.

As an investigation journalist for over 20 years, the first author of this paper, Ramona Rosulescu, has documented the management of the mining industry from Jiu Valley.

The debts of the National Bituminous Company (CNH) reached 4.67 billion lei, increasing by 13% compared to the level registered at the end of December. The National Bituminous Company no longer benefited from state subsidies. It has been operating from its own resources for 10 months.

(11.10.2011- SNLO registered a profit of 41 million while CNH continues to "burn empty")

A Romanian delegation led by Minister Ion Ariton participated, for three days, in China in a series of meetings with companies interested in investing in the Romanian energy sector. The general director of CNH, Constantin Jujan, and the general director of Termoelectrica, Florin Mârza, were part of the Romanian delegation.

(22.10.2011 - China Coal Equipment and Engineering, interested in investing in the Jiu Valley mines)

"On Monday, October 31, 2011, National Bituminous Company will make the payment of the first installment of compensatory salaries due to the laid-off persons who left the system at the beginning of this month, following the application of the CNH Reorganization and Restructuring Program for 2011", says a press release of CNH Petroșani.

(30.10.2011 - Week with money for laid-off miners 900 former miners will receive compensatory wages, unemployment benefits and supplementary income this week)

Figure 8. 26 years of evolution of the Coal Production in Jiu Valley measured in number of tons

(source – Hunedoara Energetic Complex)

Thus, if in the fall of 1997, almost 20,000 miners from Jiu Valley were left without a job, after the first and hardest series of collective layoffs in Romania, later numerous layoffs of thousands of other miners reduced the number of employees, so the company reduced its staff over 10 times in 26 years. But the decrease in production was much more dramatic than the reduction in personnel, with numerous subjective factors contributing to its decrease.

Hunedoara Energetic Complex was established based on Government Decision no. 1023/2011 (12.10.2011) following the merger procedure between Electrocentrale Deva S.A., Electrocentrale Paroşeni S.A. and the National Society of Huilei S.A. Hunedoara Energetic Complex (insolvent since 2019) - has debts of 1.8 billion lei and ranks third in the list of debtors to the Romanian state. State companies have debts of almost 20 billion lei to the budget, according to ANAF information, it is about 1,718 economic operators, so 35% of the total belongs to CNH and CEH. CEH's disappearance in the fog lasted almost 5 years (2019-2024), and the first author of the work identified and documented through journalistic investigations during the years 2022-2023, some of the causes that aggravated the economic situation of the company, a situation that finally led to the disappearance of CEH.

Figure 9. 26 years of evolution of the Coal Production in Jiu Valley for the remaining mines in year 2024, measured in number of tons (source – Hunedoara Energetic Complex)

Clean dirty! Absolutely sensational realization of a mining operation in Jiu Valley that will remain in the annals of the Hunedoara Energy Complex with a production of "-90 tons" of coal mined in a day. In other words, for all the rest of us non-specialists this could mean that the miners have "glued the coal back into the deposit"

(27.11.2019 - Absolute record. A mine in Jiu Valley exploited "-100 tons" of coal in one day)

After distinguishing itself in economic theory by restructuring (with compensatory payments) "retirees or pensioners", not positions, CEH manages manage to ironize any calculation with a ridiculous coal production. One day in November 2019, a mining unit was listed with "-100" tons of coal". Yesterday - Wednesday, the same unit managed to register a new record. The miners took the coal out of the underground with their pockets. That is exactly 16 tons. Why?

(24.03.2022 - The 624 employees at the Livezeni Mine produced, in one day, 16 tons of coal. The director's brother, newly hired at CEH)

Figure 10. 26 years of evolution of the Coal Production in Jiu Valley containing the remaining mines in year 2024, measured in number of tons (source – Hunedoara Energetic Complex)

The special administrator of CEH, Cristian Roșu, stated, on Monday, for Gazeta de dimineață, that the Ministry of Energy is currently continuing negotiations for CEH to obtain state aid and for the "closure of the underground" which in this procedural phase is not put into safety. That is, until now, no underground closure works have been carried out either at the Lonea mine or at the Lupeni mine.

(28.03.2022 - The aid given by the Government to CEH cannot be used for underground works. The normative act only refers to "surface works")

The energy company from Jiu Valley will receive 50 million lei from the budget reserve fund to cover some operating expenses. The money will be used once the state completes the payment of the viable assets of the CEH and the Jiu Valley Energy Complex becomes operational. It is not the first time that the state gives money to CEH. Last year, from the salary receivables guarantee fund, the company received millions of lei for the payment of salaries. This despite the fact that CEH, an insolvent company, did not contribute even one leu.

(22.09.2023 - State piggy bank, opened for CEH. The energy company receives over 60 million lei. Another 300 million lei are prepared)

A stone's throw from DN66A, across the road from the Paroșeni Thermal Power Station, the coal found on the surface, on private land, is exploited. The "miners" are supported in their activity by machines that remove the first layer of earth. The police from Vulcan caught some workers and the machines on the spot. The approximately 50 bags of coal were found in the area. The land belongs to a man from Vulcan, Viorel Moga, and the machines belong to the Răscol Transport company, managed by Florin Răscol. The latter is the son of PSD senator Cristian Resmerita. Florin Răscol stated for Gazeta de dimineață that he was carrying out work on private land.

(14.12.2023 - Coal mining across the street from the Paroșeni Thermal Power Station. The police found the coal in bags)

Figure 11. 18 years of comparative evolution of production and employees in the mining industry

(source – Romanian National Institute of Statistics and Hunedoara Energetic Complex)

The Ministry of Energy decided to amend and complete the constitutive act of the former Jiu Valley National Mine Closure Company and created the Jiu Valley Energy Complex Company. The new CEVJ society started its activity under extremely gloomy auspices, let's see what the end will be...

Ion Nemeş, the director of the Livezeni mine, was detained on Thursday by DIICOT prosecutors. The detention of the director of the mining unit comes about two weeks after the DIICOT prosecutors and the police from the fight against organized crime descended on the Jiu Valley Energy Complex, the Livezeni mine, the Lonea mine, the Prestserv headquarters and the residences of some employees, including the home of the general manager. Miners talk about illegal practices, established over time. Employees who no longer had their cards, which were kept by their bosses. Businessmen who were employed at the mine for seniority, but whose money was collected by the bosses. DIICOT confiscated large sums of money, phones, and gold from the homes of CEVJ employees.

(18.07.2024 - Director of the Livezeni mine, detained by DIICOT)

Probably this is the cause why in the last 18 years, the production decreased five times, while the number of personal decreased only 3 times!

Solutions for the Jiu Valley Companies for the 2025-2040 years - Adaptive management proposed for the energy transition in Jiu Valley region

The wind industry and the photovoltaic industry in Romania have the ambition to contribute to a fair energy transition and propose ambitious training and professional conversion projects for people from areas dependent on the coal energy production sector and beyond. (The Jiu Valley and the Oltenia basin and other counties where renewable energy is developing. During the courses, the reconversion of technicians and specialists in wind, photovoltaic and electricity distribution is targeted.

Figure 12. Platform for Carboniferous Regions in Transition

The technical and professional skills of the technicians in the mining sector, but also those employed in other industries, are easily transferable to the renewable energy and energy distribution sector, and the certifications obtained following the training and conversion courses will allow them to work in the installation, operation and maintenance of renewable projects and electrical networks around the world, with attractive salary benefits.

According to European statistics and trends, the installed capacity of renewables doubles every year, there is an immediate but also medium and long-term need for the training of new specialists. The RENEWACAD initiative has so far trained around 10,000 people, to international standards (it is a member of the GWO-Global Wind Organization), a figure that also includes those whom the standards force to return to training every year for some specializations. More than 95% of the specialists in renewables - mainly wind energy - from Romania, work on a project basis abroad and return to Romania monthly, generating incomes well above the average of the areas they come from.

Figure 13. Training time schedule in the field of renewable energy (reconversion of technicians and specialists in wind, photovoltaic and electricity distribution)

RENEWACAD projects in the Jiu Valley area are part of an integrated development strategy, aligned with the development plan of the Jiu Valley microregion. There is submitted for financing, through the Just Transition Program, a project for the construction of an assembly plant for equipment components in the renewable energy industry. This project aims to build a factory in the town of Petrila, which will create 42 new jobs and contribute to the urban regeneration of the former Petrila Mine. Another project, financed from RENEWACAD sources, focuses on building an energy storage system in batteries, intended to help balance the national energy system. This investment will also take place in the city of Petrila, Hunedoara county.

Conclusions

Even if the world trend from the recent years did not support coal mining, Jiu Valley was the example of the managerial disaster. The 9 passages from the numerous journalistic investigations carried out by the first author of this paper in the last 15 years, can indirectly demonstrate the decrease of coal production to an almost insignificant level. Rusty products, lost money from the state budget, possible thefts are just some of the aspects identified that definitely led to the present situation. Maybe the future of Jiu Valley would have been the same, but certainly this managerial disaster has made coal no longer definitely a source of income for Jiu Valley, and the only solution can be offered by a transition from mining to another industry.

The solution for the transition of Jiu Valley from mining as a mono-industrial activity to other industrial activities can be offered by a plan coordinated by the municipalities of the Jiu Valley, taking into account both local peculiarities and global perspectives. The opening of production facilities in the field of renewable energy can generate jobs, but this measure represent only one direction of development for a just transition. Jiu Valley needs dozens of such concrete projects that provide the conditions for the transition to green energy but also to save the inhabitants of this area.

References

Cardoso, A.,

2015

Behind the life cycle of coal: Socio-environmental liabilities of coal mining in Cesar, Colombia Ecologic Economy, 120, pp. 71–82.

Dale, B.,

2002

An institutional approach to local restructuring: The case of four Norwegian mining towns, European Urban and Regional Studies, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 5-20.

Haney, M.; Shkaratan, M.,

2013

Mine Closure and its Impact on the Community: Five Years After Mine Closure in Romania, Russia, and Ukraine, World Bank Policy Res. Work. Pap. 42, pp 80-86.

Horváth, G.; Csüllög, G. Salgótarján A.,

2012

The Rise and Fall of a Mining and Industrial Region, Problems and Potentials of Post-Mining Regions, in Post-Mining Regions in Central Europe—Problems, Potentials, Possibilities, München, Germany, pp. 40–52.

Radu B.,

2016

Aspects on the Transformation and Decline of Mining Communities in Romania, Journal of Settlements and Spatial Planning, vol. 7, no. 2, Cluj Napoca.

Strangleman, T.,

2001

Networks, place and identities in post-industrial mining communities, *International Journal of Urban Research*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 253-267.

<https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20220413-how-ending-mining-would-change-the-world>

<https://www.mining.com/mining-industry-risks-another-lost-decade/>

https://www.deloitte.com/content/dam/assets-shared/legacy/docs/gx-Tracking-the-trends-2023_Digital_V2.pdf

<https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/metals-and-mining/our-insights/has-mining-lost-its-luster-why-talent-is-moving-elsewhere-and-how-to-bring-them-back>

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?qid=1593086905382&uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0102>

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/swd-competitive-clean-european-steel_en.pdf

<https://wind-technicians.com/ro/renewacad/>